

FROM FIELD TO MOON: ANALOG RADIOCHEMICAL MAPPING OF VOLCANIC TERRAINS WITH PORTABLE GRNS FOR THE LUNAR-VISE MISSION. Deniz Ölçek^{1,2,9}, Craig Hardgrove², Thomas Prettyman³, Kerri L. Donaldson Hanna⁴, Kristen A. Bennett⁵, Lena Heffern⁶, Margaret Landis², Amber L. Gullikson⁷, Naoyuki Yamashita³, Victoria Concepcion², Erik Johnson⁸, and the Lunar-VISE Team

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Introduction: The study of lunar silicic volcanism is central to understanding the Moon’s thermal and magmatic evolution. Naturally occurring radioelements—potassium (K), thorium (Th), and uranium (U)—are incompatible trace elements that preferentially concentrate in residual melts during fractional crystallization, making them sensitive tracers of magmatic differentiation [1]. Orbital gamma-ray and neutron spectroscopy (GRNS) has mapped these elements globally [2], but the spatial footprint of orbital measurements limits the ability to resolve small silicic constructs such as the Gruithuisen Domes. Forward modeling suggests elevated Th at Mons Gruithuisen Gamma (up to ~43 ppm), consistent with evolved lithologies [3]. The Lunar Vulkan Imaging and Spectroscopy Explorer (Lunar-VISE) mission will directly test these hypotheses through in situ measurements at Mons Gruithuisen Gamma using a rover-borne gamma-ray and neutron spectrometer (LV-GRNS) to constrain Th abundance and the regolith neutron response along the traverse [4]. In preparation for Lunar-VISE, we conducted two complementary terrestrial analog campaigns using portable GRNS systems at (1) the San Francisco Volcanic Field (SFVF), Arizona, and (2) the Wildcat Hills, Utah—compositionally diverse analog sites used to validate rover-relevant GRNS measurement strategies [8].

Methods: We conducted analog field campaigns in (1) the San Francisco Volcanic Field (SFVF), Arizona, spanning rhyolitic to basaltic units (Sugarloaf Mountain, Bonito Lava Flow, Robinson Mountain), and (2) the Wildcat Hills, Utah, a silicic volcanic complex with rhyolite and dacite outcrops, using a portable dual-detector system based on NaI(Tl) and CLYC scintillators. At SFVF (Fig. 1), measurements targeted Sugarloaf Mountain (rhyolitic dome), Bonito Lava Flow (basaltic), and Robinson Mountain (basaltic/intermediate) to quantify K, U, and Th variability across various volcanic terrain [8]. At Wildcat Hills (Fig. 2), we collected analogous datasets across rhyolitic and dacitic units (including cavity and boulder measurements) to extend the analog framework to silicic dome terrains with strong lithologic contrasts at meter scales relevant to rover-borne GRNS measurements.

Results: Regionally averaged radioelement abundances derived from SFVF gamma-ray spectroscopy show strong compositional separation between silicic and basaltic terrains: Sugarloaf Mountain exhibits the highest concentrations (K: 3.29±0.24 wt.%, U: 14.35±1.81 ppm,

Th: 27.14±2.43 ppm), while Bonito Lava Flow (K: 1.13±0.08 wt.%, U: 3.86±0.52 ppm, Th: 7.52±1.02 ppm) and Robinson Mountain (K: 1.46±0.16 wt.%, U: 5.59±1.06 ppm, Th: 11.75±1.98 ppm) are lower and consistent with basaltic compositions [8]. Gamma-ray fluxes at Sugarloaf are elevated by ~3–4× relative to nearby basaltic units, consistent with magmatic differentiation trends. Meter-scale geometry also matters: a measurement adjacent to a >10 m cliff face at Sugarloaf yielded ~28% higher Th than a point 3–5 m away, demonstrating proximity/topographic enhancement and/or localized compositional heterogeneity [8].

Figure 1: (Left) Handheld gamma-ray and neutron detector instrument positioned inside a cavity at the Bonito Lava Flow. (Right) Field setup at the San Francisco Volcanic Field (SFVF), with Sugarloaf Mountain in the background.

At Wildcat Hills, short-acquisition measurements resolve K, U and Th variations across rhyolite and dacite units made of boulders and cavities, and proximity experiments indicate that measurements within ~1 m of an outcrop can help separate rock composition from surrounding soils; K/Th ratios provide an additional discriminator between dacite and rhyolite at rover-scale standoffs [5].

Implications: Together, these two analog field campaigns demonstrate that portable GRNS systems can quantitatively resolve compositional variability at multiple scales: factors of ~3–4× between basaltic and silicic units, and meter-scale proximity enhancements on the order of ~10–30% in complex terrain. The measured SFVF concentrations are consistent with published geochemical constraints for regional volcanic units [6,7], supporting the robustness of the field methodology.

Figure 2. (Left) Handheld dual-detector instrument acquiring measurements inside a rhyolite cavity. (Right) Measurements beside a dacite breccia boulder at the Wildcat Hills, Utah.

These results provide a field-validated framework for interpreting Lunar-VICE LV-GRNS measurements, in which continuous observations during rover drives and longer stationary integrations will be used to identify traverse segments with varying Th and H abundances and neutron-absorption signatures [4]. More broadly, the demonstrated ability to discriminate major rock types and resolve compositional gradients supports the feasibility of rover-borne GRNS for identifying evolved lithologies and constraining the Moon's volcanic history, with relevance to Lunar-VICE and future rover concepts (e.g., Endurance-A and the Canadian Lunar Rover Mission).

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